

Studies on photoelectrochemical conversion[†]

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Studies on photoelectrochemical conversion based on polycrystalline semiconducting materials prepared using electrochemical co-deposition techniques are briefly reviewed. Systems based on metal chalcogenides and mixed metal chalcogenides have been dealt with. Electrochemical studies on photoelectroactive materials prepared using mixed solvents and photoelectro-convertibility studies on some multiple band gap composite semiconducting systems are also presented.

The sun bestows its bounty on earth incessantly. Possibility of collecting and using solar energy to supplement the continually dwindling energy sources has been receiving increasing attention for the past quite sometime. A major step towards the realization of this objective has been achieved by solar converters, the photovoltaic cells. Their price, however, is prohibitive and are therefore still of little competitive significance for terrestrial applications.

Alternatives to all solid state solar cells are being sought. Efforts are being made to develop photoelectrochemical cells for direct conversion of solar energy either into electricity or chemical energy. Some photoelectrochemical systems have been proposed which have reasonable conversion efficiencies¹⁻⁴. It has not yet been possible to construct a device of practical utility, mainly because potentially useful photoelectroactive materials which absorb solar energy, lack durability.

Numerous techniques have been used for the preparation of semiconducting materials for studying their suitability in photoelectrochemical conversions⁵⁻¹⁰. Single crystal preparations endowed with attractive photoelectro-convertibility have been reported. From a practical viewpoint large area semiconducting electrodes based on polycrystalline materials are required. One of the methods considered eminently suitable for the preparation of photoelectroactive semiconducting materials is that of electrochemical co-deposition. We have used electrochemical co-deposition for the preparation of polycrystalline materials for the purpose of investigating their photoelectrochemical characteristics to explore possibilities of their use in light energized conversion devices. A brief description of the electrochemical basis of co-deposition follows.

Electrochemical co-deposition

For deposition of an ion it is essential that its normal deposition potential given by

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln a \quad (1)$$

is reached; E^0 is the standard potential. In order to bring about the discharge of two or more ions together, it is essential that their deposition potentials are brought to identical values¹¹. This can be accomplished by suitable adjustment of ionic activities. It is, however obvious that this will be possible only if normal deposition potentials of the ions do not differ much. Eqn. (1) clearly shows that a ten-fold change in activity of a divalent ion can alter its potential by about 30 mV at ambient temperature. Electrochemical co-deposition can not thus be expected in many cases of practical interest. This difficulty can, however be overcome if electrochemical co-deposition is carried out under limiting current. During electrochemical co-deposition the ions being discharged are brought to the electrode by diffusion and normal process of transference. Under limiting current density condition, the diffusional transport will exclusively regulate the discharge of ions. If the current density is progressively increased, a stage is reached when a sudden change in electrode potential is observed. This indicates that the limiting current for the more electropositive ion is reached. As the potential is increased beyond this value, the discharge of less electropositive ions will also take place. Electrochemical co-deposition thus becomes possible. In practice, it is essential to investigate current-voltage behavior to identify the deposition potential range within which electrochemical activity occurs. Electrodeposition is then carried out using different deposition potentials within this range. These deposits are tested for their functional activity to ascertain the optimal conditions under which electrochemical co-deposition may be subsequently be carried out.

A condensed review based on our work on photoelectrochemical conversions is presented here.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Photoelectrochemical studies on metal chalcogenides

Metal chalcogenides are attractive systems for photoelectric conversions¹²⁻¹⁵. Cadmium chalcogenides¹⁶⁻¹⁹ have been extensively studied to accomplish such conversions in photoelectrochemical cells. These materials invariably exhibit *n*-type semiconductivity and behave as photoanodes upon illumination. From the point of view of solar energy conversion, *p*-type materials endowed with acceptable stability and compatibility are also required so that enhanced photoresponsiveness upon illumination may become possible. We have prepared zinc selenide electrodes by electrochemical co-deposition using limiting currents and investigated their photoelectroactivity. All preparations exhibit *p*-type semiconductivity in zinc sulfate solutions containing I_2/I_3^- redox couple²⁰⁻²². Some representative data are given in Fig. 1. The observed variation in photoelectroactivity of different electrodes prepared under identical experimental conditions is perhaps caused by inhomogeneous layer thickness of the electrode. Optical excitation of the semiconduc-

Fig. 1. Photoelectroactivity of different zinc selenide electrodes; 0.01 M SeO_2 was used in all preparations.

tor causes separation of electrons and holes. It appears that the photogenerated holes also participate in the oxidizing reaction with the electrolyte species in solution. That is why the recorded photopotentials, E_p are much lower than that expected on the basis of the Fermi level of the semiconductor, E_F and E^0 , the oxidation potential of the redox system^{23,24},

$$E_p = E_F - E^0 \quad (2)$$

Dissipation through short-circuiting results in an impairment of the functional activity of the electrodes. A significant sample to sample variation in the morphology of the film could also lead to different results.

The semiconductor electrolyte interfacial region is endowed with electrical heterogeneity on account of the existence of a depletion layer on the semiconductor side and a diffused double layer on the solution side. The overall capacitance of this system of photoelectric activity is made up of two distinct contributions from the space charge region existing on either side of the interface. In view of relatively much lower charge carrier density in the depletion layer, the experimentally measured capacitance of the semiconductor electrolyte interfacial region is attributed to the semiconductor alone. The charge distribution in the depletion layer is altered when semiconductor potential is varied. The semiconductor capacitance thus depends on the electrode potential. This dependence is usually expressed in terms of Mott-Schottky relationship,

$$\frac{1}{C_{SC}^2} = \frac{2}{\epsilon \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot q \cdot N_D} (E - E_{fb}) \quad (3)$$

where N_D is the charge carrier density, ϵ and ϵ_0 are the dielectric constant of the semiconductor and vacuum, q is the electronic charge and E_{fb} the flat band potential. According to this relationship, $1/C_{SC}^2$ vs E plots should be linear with slope = $2/\epsilon \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot q \cdot N_D$. Furthermore, $E = E_{fb}$ when $1/C_{SC}^2 = 0$. The N_D and E_{fb} values obtained from Mott-Schottky plots in this manner along with photopotential values for some zinc selenide preparations are included in Table 1. The photoresponsiveness of these materials is obviously not attractive. Zinc selenide has a band gap of 2.7 eV. It is, therefore, of some interest to combine it with some

Table 1. Photoelectroactivity, flat-band potential and donor density of some typical zinc selenide preparations

Mol. comp. of electroplating soln.	E_p mV	E_{fb}^* V	N_D 10^{15} cm^{-3}
ZnSO ₄ : SeO ₂			
0.005 : 0.01	135	0.75	9.0
0.0075 : 0.01	200	0.69	8.8
0.010 : 0.01	397	0.57	7.0
0.015 : 0.01	115	0.55	9.5
0.020 : 0.01	115	0.54	7.0

*Versus saturated calomel electrode.

suitable *n*-type semiconducting electrode to form a heterojunction photoelectrochemical cell. Such a cell using cadmium selenide in conjunction with zinc selenide was fabricated and its photoresponse studied to adjudge its suitability for photoelectric conversions. The cell may be represented as

Photopotential build up and decay plots are shown in Fig. 2. The initial rates of build-up of photopotential along with photoelectroactivity of ZnSe, CdSe and ZnSe/CdSe are in-

Fig. 2. Photopotential build-up and decay curves for *p-n* PEC cell :
 (1) *n*-CdSe | 1 M Cd(CH₃COO)₂ + 0.01 M KI + 50 mM I₂ | Pt
 (2) *p*-ZnSe | 2 M ZnSO₄ + 0.1 M KI + 50 mM I₂ | Pt
 (3) *n*-CdSe | 1 M Cd(CH₃COO)₂ + 0.1 M KI + 50 mM I₂ ||
 2 M ZnSO₄ + 0.1 M KI + 50 mM I₂ | *p*-ZnSe

cluded in Table 2. R_b^i denotes initial rate of build-up of photopotential and I_p the observed photocurrent. These results clearly show that enhanced photoresponsiveness is obtained upon simultaneous illumination of both the electrodes.

Electrode system	E_p mV	R_b^i mV s ⁻¹	I_p μ A
ZnSe/Pt	385	1700	27.2
CdSe/Pt	315	1750	30.7
ZnSe/CdSe	670	3250	97.0

We also explored possibility of enhancing photoelectroactivity of zinc selenide by electrochemical incorporation of thallium²⁵. A priori considerations suggest that incorporation of thallium should enhance *p*-type semiconductivity of zinc selenide²⁶. Photoaction spectral studies reveal that the threshold wavelength values in the case of zinc selenide and thallium containing zinc selenide are 570 and 710 nm, respectively. Thus incorporation of thallium results in lowering of the band gap of zinc selenide which in turn indicates possibility of enhancement of the capture and conversion of light into electricity. This is borne out by the experimental results on photoelectroactivity presented in

Fig. 3. Furthermore, no impairment in functional activity occurs during the period of investigation.

Fig. 3. Functional stability of TI-doped zinc selenide electrode under intermittent illumination.

We also explored possibilities of modification of zinc selenide to bring down its band gap to obtain enhanced photoresponsiveness²⁷ by inclusion of tellurium during its electroynthesis. Photoelectrochemical characteristics of zinc selenide electrodeposits containing tellurium are summarized in Table 3. The band gap of zinc selenide is seen to decrease with increase in tellurium content. Thus there is a distinct possibility of increased optical absorption with tellurium inclusion as evidenced by photoelectroactivity data.

Table 3. Photoelectrochemical characteristics of zinc selenide electrodes containing tellurium

Mol. comp. of electroplating soln.	N_D 10 ¹⁸ cm ⁻³	E_{fb} V	Band gap eV
Zn : Se : Te			
1 : 0.1 : 0.00	55	-1.20	2.30
1 : 0.1 : 0.01	28	-1.00	2.10
1 : 0.1 : 0.02	23	-0.90	1.70
1 : 0.1 : 0.03	74	-0.85	1.90

Studies on mixed metal chalcogenides

Electrosynthesis of mixed chalcogenides in principle, is possible if deposition potentials of their constituents are brought to identical values or a potential in excess of the deposition potential of the most electropositive ion is applied. The quality of the electrodeposits from the point of view of photoelectrochemical conversion depends on the deposition potential and composition of the electroplating solution. Even when these variables are kept fixed, photoresponsiveness of the electrodeposits obtained using the same substrate, may vary widely. This is attributed to compositional heterogeneity and structural and morphological dissimilarities. Current-voltage studies in conjunction with photoelectroactivity studies reveal that (ZnCd)Se elec-

trodeposit exhibits enhanced activity when electrosynthesis is carried out using deposition potential of -0.70 V vs SCE²⁸.

It may be pointed out that when electrosynthesis is carried out at fixed potential, the deposition current declines somewhat rapidly initially and eventually approaches a time-invariant value. The swiftness with which deposition current declines may be expressed in terms of $t_{1/2}$, the time needed for the deposition current to approach half of its initial value. This parameter measures progress of coverage of the substrate and should have some correlation with the quality of the electrodeposit from the point of view of its photoelectroconvertibility. A low value of $t_{1/2}$ may be attributed to increased coverage and uniformly growing films having morphological evenness. The results included in Fig. 4 show that (ZnCd)Se films for which $t_{1/2}$ is low are indeed endowed with increased photoactivity. These electrodeposits may be visualized as solid solutions of ZnSe and CdSe. A lowering of band gap is expected with progressive inclusion of cadmium in the electrodeposit. Band gap values estimated on the basis of photoaction spectral studies are found to be consistent with this expectation.

Fig. 4. Typical photopotential versus $t_{1/2}$ plot. All preparations were carried out at -0.70 V vs SCE.

Cadmium selenide is endowed with attractive photoelectroconvertibility because of compatibility of its absorption spectrum with that of visible part of the solar spectrum²⁹. Adducts such as (CdHg)Te have been shown to be of considerable interest from the point of view of some practical applications. We attempted to prepare (CdHg)Se films of variable composition by electrochemical means to investigate the effect of progressive inclusion of mercury of the band gap of the electrodeposits³⁰. The nature of the semiconductivity of the (CdHg)Se electrodeposits depends on composition of the electroplating solution and the deposition potential. An inversion from *p* to *n* type semicon-

ductivity was observed with progressive inclusion of mercury in the electrodeposit. The band gap depends on composition of the electroplating solution. Increase in mercury content results in lowering of the band gap of the electrodeposited (CdHg)Se (Fig. 5). The covalent radii of Cd and Hg are comparable (*ca.* 1.48 Å) and accordingly the adduct (CdHg)Se is expected to be a solid solution³¹ of CdSe and HgSe. The band gap is not proportional to the concentration of Hg^{2+} ion possibly because Hg content in the electrodeposit is different from the content of Hg^{2+} in the electroplating solution as was found in some similar cases.

Fig. 5. Band gap values for different (CdHg)Se films.

We also carried out preparation and characterization of (CdGa)Se of variable composition³². These electrodeposits are endowed with *p*-type semiconductivity. The band gap of the electrodeposits depends on composition; it decreases with increase in Ga content of the electroplating solution. It appears that (CdGa)Se is a solid solution of cadmium selenide and zinc selenide.

Photoelectrochemical studies using mixed solvents

Polycrystalline semiconductor electrodeposits obtained by electrolyzing aqueous solutions under potentiostatic or galvanostatic control invariably contain microscopic cracks due to accompanying splitting of water³³. This problem, in principle, can be obviated to some extent by using water–nonaqueous solvent mixtures; and there is additionally a distinct possibility of increase in the usable deposition potential range³⁴. Electrodeposition of cadmium selenide was carried out employing different current densities for desired time-intervals using water–dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) mixtures of variable composition. During galvanostatic deposition, the deposition potential varies with time in all cases. It decreases less rapidly with increase in concentration of

DMSO in the electroplating solution. This indicates reduction in polarization with increase in nonaqueous content of the electroplating solution. Consequently, compositionally less inhomogeneous electrodeposits are expected in this mixed solvent system.

The electrodeposited CdSe films obtained using 95% water and 5% DMSO mixtures were studied for their photoelectroconvertibility using I_2/I_3^- and $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ redox couple. The results are shown in Fig. 6. The electrodeposits show improved photoactivity when $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ redox system is used³⁵. In both the cases, maximum photoactivity is observed with preparations obtained using current density of 0.4 mA cm^{-2} for 10 min. However, there is one conspicuous difference. All preparations exhibit *n*-type semiconductivity in $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}/[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ redox system. In I_2/I_3^- redox system, on the other hand, *p*-type semiconducting behavior is observed at low current densities while only *n*-type semiconductivity is shown at current densities beyond 0.3 mA cm^{-2} .

Fig. 6. Variation of photopotential with composition of water + DMSO mixtures used to prepare electroplating solutions : (○) 0.2 mA cm^{-2} for 15 min and (●) 0.4 mA cm^{-2} for 10 min; testing solution : $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + 0.01 \text{ M K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6 + 0.01 \text{ M K}_3\text{Fe(CN)}_6$.

Photoelectrochemical studies on multiple band gap materials

The preparation of some multiple band gap semicon-

ductor films based on CdSe and ZnSe was carried out using galvanostatic electrochemical co-deposition techniques to investigate their photoelectrochemical characteristics on the basis of photoelectroconvertibility and photoaction spectral studies³⁶. CdSe exhibits attractive photoactivity because of compatibility of its band gap with solar spectrum but has been found to be susceptible to corrosion^{37,38}. ZnSe, on the other hand, is endowed with acceptable resistance towards corrosion but its photoexcitability is confined only to high frequencies because of its relatively wide band gap³⁹⁻⁴¹. Coupling of cadmium selenide and zinc selenide is expected to provide a multiple band gap semiconductor which may be suitable for accomplishing the twin tasks of increased absorption of solar spectrum and enhanced resistance towards electrochemical corrosion. We explored the possibility of preparation of some multiple band gap semiconductor film electrodes based on CdSe and ZnSe using galvanostatic co-deposition technique. Following configurations were attempted : (i) A CdSe layer was deposited using titanium foil; this was followed by the electrodeposition of ZnSe using different current densities for various time intervals. (ii) Titanium-supported mixed metal (CdZn)Se films were prepared using different current densities.

These composite systems show substantially improved photoelectrochemical properties compared to the constituent CdSe and ZnSe films prepared under comparable experimental conditions (Tables 4 and 5). These results clearly show that the presence of zinc selenide in conjunction with electrodeposited cadmium selenide films results in considerably enhanced photoactivity, especially when the electrodeposition of zinc selenide is carried out under galvanostatic control using current densities in the range $0.3\text{--}1.0 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$. This obviously indicates absorption and

Table 4. Photoactivity data of the mixed (CdZn)Se system*

Electroplating solution : $0.05 \text{ M CdSO}_4 + 0.001 \text{ M SeO}_2 +$ varying concentrations of ZnSO_4

Deposition current density mA cm^{-2}	Photopotential (mV)		
	0.01 M ZnSO_4	0.03 M ZnSO_4	0.05 M ZnSO_4
0.1	435	528	625
0.2	565	570	610
0.3	560	585	590
0.4	462	478	535
0.8	445	485	535
1.0	425	470	482

*Deposition time = 10 min; testing solution : $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + 0.01 \text{ M K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6 + 0.01 \text{ M K}_3\text{Fe(CN)}_6$.

Table 5. Photoresponsiveness of CdSe/ZnSe electrodes*

Electroplating solutions 0.01 M CdSO₄ + 0.001 M SeO₂ for CdSe and 0.01 M ZnSO₄ + 0.001 M SeO₂ for ZnSe

Exptl conditions for deposition of CdSe		Exptl conditions for deposition of ZnSe		Photopotential mV CdSe/ZnSe system
Deposition mA cm ⁻²	Deposition min	Deposition mA cm ⁻²	Deposition min	
		0.1		220
		0.2		460
0.1	10	0.3	15	440
		0.4		445
		0.8		445
		1.0		450

*Testing solution 0.5 M Cd(CH₃COO)₂ + 0.1 M ZnSO₄ + 0.1 M KI + 0.2 mM I₂

photoexcitation by electromagnetic radiations from within a broader range of the electromagnetic spectrum. The results given in Fig. 7 support the contention that photoactivity of the composite system is a consequence of the photoexcitation of both the semiconductor layers. Threshold wavelengths for CdSe and ZnSe, 730 and 550 nm, respectively, correspond to band gap values of 1.7 and 2.4 eV. In this composite system, the photoexcitation of ZnSe dominates till $\lambda = 550$ nm beyond which photoexcitation of both ZnSe and CdSe seems to be involved.

Fig. 7. Photoaction spectral data (O) CdSe/ZnSe, (●) CdSe, (Δ) ZnSe

The studies presented herein show that the multiple band

gap electrodeposited films obtained under galvanostatic control exhibit improved photoelectroconvertibility. Furthermore, current-voltage behavior reveals that the both the photoelectroactive systems are endowed with substantially improved resistance towards electrochemical corrosion.

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References

- 1 "Photoelectrochemical Conversion and Storage of Solar Energy", ed J S Connolly, Academic, New York, 1981
- 2 "Preparation and Characterization of Materials", eds J M Honig and C N R Rao, Academic, New York, 1981
- 3 S Chandra, "Photoelectrochemical Cells", Gordon and Breach, 1980
- 4 "Photoeffects at Semiconductor-Electrolyte Interfaces", ed A J Nozik, American Chemical Society, Washington D C, 1981
- 5 A Heller, G P Schwartz, R G Vadimsky, S Menezes and B Miller, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1978, **125**, 1156
- 6 R M Moore, *Solar Energy*, 1976, **18**, 225
- 7 R Memming and F Mollers, *Ber Bunsenges Phys Chem*, 1972, **76**, 475
- 8 A B Ellis, S W Kaser and M S Wrighton, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1976, **98**, 1635
- 9 B Miller and A Heller, *Nature*, 1976, **262**, 680
- 10 G Hodes, D Cohen, J Manasser and M David, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1980, **127**, 2252
- 11 A T Vagramyan and Z A Solo'eva, "Technology of Electrodeposition", Robert Draper, Teddington, 1961, p 127
- 12 S Yae, I Nakarishi, Y Nakato, N Toshima and H Mori, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1994, **141**, 3077
- 13 T Torimoto, R J Fox and M A Fox, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1996, **143**, 3712
- 14 N S Lewis, *Electrochem Soc (Interface)*, 1996, **5**, 28
- 15 N R de Tacconi, H Wenren and K Rajeshwar, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1997, **144**, 3159
- 16 B Miller, A Heller, M Robins, S Menezes, K C Chang and J Thomason, Jr, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1977, **124**, 1019
- 17 D Ham, K K Misra and K Rajeshwar, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1991, **138**, 100
- 18 V Marcue and H H Strehblow, *J Electrochem Soc* 1991, **138**, 758
- 19 Ph Allongne and R Tenne, *J Electrochem Soc*, 1991, **138**, 261
- 20 K Singh and J P Rai, *Phys Stat Sol (A)*, 1987, **99**, 257

Singh.: Studies on photoelectrochemical conversion

21. K. Singh and J. P. Rai, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 1985, **4**, 1401.
22. K. Singh and R. K. Pathak, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1991, **7**, 326.
23. I. S. Tonaka, J. A. Bruce and M. S. Wrighton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 3778.
24. G. S. Calabrese and M. S. Wrighton, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 6273.
25. K. Singh and J. P. Rai, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 557.
26. "Polycrystalline and Amorphous Thin Films and Devices", ed. L. L. Kazmerski, Academic, New York, 1980, p. 219.
27. K. Singh and R. K. Pathak, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 55.
28. K. Singh and A. K. Shukla, *Sol. Eng. Mat. Sol. Cells*, 1993, **30**, 169.
29. M. S. Wrighton, A. B. Ellis and S. W. Kaiser, *Adv. Chem. Ser.*, 1977, **163**, 71.
30. K. Singh and Md. R. Tanveer, *J. Mat. Chem.*, 1993, **3**, 1295.
31. N. B. Hannay, "Solid State Chemistry", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1967, p.14.
32. K. Singh and Md. R. Tanveer, *Sol. Eng. Mat. Sol. Cells*, 1995, **36**, 409.
33. A. C. Rastogi and K. S. Balakrishnan, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1989, **136**, 1502.
34. "Laboratory Techniques in Electroanalytical Chemistry", eds. P. T. Kissinger and W. R. Heneman, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1984, p. 328.
35. K. Singh and S. S. D. Mishra, *Sol. Eng. Mat. Sol. Cells*, 2000, **63**, 275.
36. K. Singh and S. S. D. Mishra, *Sol. Eng. Mat. Sol. Cells*, 2002, **71**, 115.
37. A. J. Bard and M. S. Wrighton, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1977, **124**, 1976.
38. H. Gerischer in "Semiconductor Liquid Junction Solar Cells", ed. A. Heller, Electrochem. Soc., New York, 1977.
39. J. M. Dona and J. Herrero, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1995, **142**, 764.
40. G. H. Schoenmakers, E. P. A. M. Bakkers and J. J. Kelly, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1997, **144**, 2329.
41. K. Singh and R. K. Pathak, *Electrochem. Acta*, 1994, **39**, 2693.

